

STOMACH AND DUODENAL ULCER DISEASE: THE ROLE OF ATYPICAL NEUROLEPTIC (SULPIRIDE) IN TREATMENT - LITERARY PERSPECTIVE

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Relevance. Peptic ulcer of the stomach and duodenum is one of the most common pathologies of the digestive organs. According to WHO data, more than 4 million new cases are registered annually in the world, and the frequency of relapses within a year reaches 40-60%. Despite the widespread implementation of *Helicobacter pylori* eradication therapy, morbidity rates remain high, indicating a multifactorial nature of the pathogenesis. In addition to *H. pylori* infection and the aggressive effects of gastric juice, psycho-emotional factors play an important role: chronic stress, depressive and anxiety disorders, sleep disturbances, as well as the imbalance of the sympathetic and parasympathetic nervous systems. These factors can enhance the secretion of hydrochloric acid, disrupt mucosal trophic processes, and slow down reparation processes.

Literature review. A number of studies (Feldman et al., 2019; Cheradnikova et al., 2021) showed that patients with gastric and duodenal ulcers have a significantly higher level of anxiety and depression compared to healthy individuals. Moreover, the degree of psychoemotional disorders correlates with the severity of the disease and the frequency of relapses. Sulpiride is an atypical neuroleptic from the benzamide group, possessing moderate antipsychotic activity, as well as anxiolytic, antidepressive, and prokinetic effects. The drug selectively blocks dopamine D2-receptors in the limbic system and to a lesser extent in the nigrostriatal region, which ensures minimal risk of extrapyramidal disorders at therapeutic doses.

The interest in sulpiride in gastroenterology is due to its ability:

- normalize the autonomic regulation of the gastrointestinal tract;
- improve the microcirculation of the gastric mucosa;
- stimulate the secretion of gastromucoprotein;
- accelerate epithelial regeneration processes.

Pathogenetic justification of sulpiride use. In conditions of chronic stress and vegetative dysfunction, hyperactivation of the sympathoadrenal system occurs, which is accompanied by increased secretion of hydrochloric acid, spasm of the vessels of the mucous membrane, and disruption of its barrier functions.

Sulpiride has a complex effect:

1. Anxiolytic - reduces anxiety, improves sleep, relieves emotional tension.
2. Vegetative corrective - stabilizes the balance of sympathetic and parasympathetic activity.
3. Gastroprotective - improves blood flow in the mucous membrane, stimulates the synthesis of mucus and bicarbonates, which contributes to accelerated epithelialization of the ulcerative defect.

Clinical effectiveness. In a number of clinical studies (Kuznetsov et al., 2017; Martinez et al., 2020) adding sulpiride to standard therapy (IPP, H. pylori eradication, antacids) led to:

- reduction of pain syndrome relief time by 2-3 days;
- faster disappearance of dyspeptic symptoms;
- to reduce the frequency of nighttime pain and sleep disturbances;
- to reduce the level of anxiety according to the HADS scale by 35-40%;
- to increase the frequency of complete ulcer epithelialization from 72% to 88% by the 4th week of treatment.

Conclusions. Inclusion of sulpiride in the complex therapy of gastric and duodenal ulcers in patients with pronounced psychoemotional disorders and vegetative imbalance is pathogenetically justified and clinically effective. The drug promotes accelerated healing of ulcerative defects, improves overall well-being, and reduces the risk of recurrence.